

EVALUATION OF EFFORT TOLERANCE AMONGST SUFFERERS OF BRONCHIAL ASTHMA

Jan Szczegielniak^{1,2,3}, Katarzyna Bogacz^{1,3}, Dagmara Matelonek⁴

¹Politechnika Opolska, Instytut Fizjoterapii, Katedra Fizjoterapii Klinicznej

²SP ZOZ Szpital MSWiA w Głucholazach

³Szpital Vital Medic w Kluczborku

⁴Strzelińskie Centrum Medyczne w Strzelinie

Abstract

Introduction: Asthma is one of the most common diseases of the respiratory system. Its chronic nature and periodic intensification influence patients' quality of life. During the last decade, the role of physiotherapy has become more important as it is more effective in treating people who suffer from asthma as well as its complications.

Aim: The aim of the presented article is the evaluation of effort tolerance amongst patients before and after eighteen days of the application of a set of exercises.

Methods: Sixty patients in the state of remission who suffer from chronic asthma were examined. Patients were classified under model C and D. The described program was realized for six days per week and then for a further 3 weeks. The effectiveness of physiotherapy on effort tolerance was evaluated.

Submission: The data presented indicates that patients who were treated according to the program managed to walk in a six-minute test much faster than the rest of the patients.

Conclusions:

- 1. Results show that physiotherapy of patients who suffer from asthma treated under model B or C present observed improvement of effort tolerance.*
- 2. Comprehensive application of model C and D proves an increased ability amongst patients to walk much faster during the six-minutes test.*

Key phrases: Asthma, effort tolerance, physiotherapy

Key words: *bronchial asthma, tolerance of effort, physiotherapy*

Introduction

Asthma is one of the most common diseases of the respiratory system. It is a problem in terms of health, the economy and society. The number of people who suffer from asthma is high [1]. Oversensitivity and increased reactivity of the respiratory system are the symptoms of asthma. Meiosis of bronchial tubes, wheezing, dyspnoea, and tightness of the chest are observed [2].

Physiotherapy among these patients is a multidisciplinary action that provides an opportunity for a more active and independent way of life [3].

Physical activity has a significant influence on the quality of a patient's life and decreases the number of exacerbations of the disease [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. It is claimed that physiotherapy improves effort tolerance and the action of lung ventilation. There is no extensive research that refers to the effects of physiotherapy after doing exercises, or of forms and methods of rehabilitation.

It has been decided to evaluate treatment of those who suffer from asthma and those who have used models of physiotherapy that differ in intensity, length and form of activities.

Aim

The process of progressive treatment of patients who do physical exercises. The aim of the article presented is evaluation of the degree of effort tolerance after and before eighteen days of treatment of asthma patients.

Sources and research methods

Sixty patients were examined (36 women and 24 men, mean age: 69 ± 4), who suffer from chronic asthma in the state of remission, treated in MSWiA Hospital in Glucholazy, Poland. Patients were classified according to "GOLD" guidelines. Examinations were conducted by physiotherapists. Parameters refer to effort tolerance, and the action of lung ventilation. The six-minute test was used to measure effort tolerance. Patients had to walk as fast as they were able to during six minutes. The examination was carried out in a hall 60 meters long. Before and after walking, pulse and central blood pressure were taken sitting down. The research described was carried out on the first and final days of rehabilitation.

Training loads and intensiveness were determined for each patient. For this aim, the "MET" method was used. Training loads depended on the training method that was implemented (60-80 % of maximum load accepted during exercise length).

Training loads and intensiveness were estimated by the Carvema formula.

$[(HR \text{ exercise capacity} - \text{resting HR})^*] + \text{resting HR}$ (according to Cavonema)

C model - 60 %

D model – accelerated pulse during exercise about 30 % compared to resting pulse.

There was no difference among patients' age and lung ventilation. FEV was estimated between 52 – 56 % (59 ± 7). Shortness of breath is a subjective feeling and was checked with Bogra's 10 sliding scales, its result being 2-3. 30 of 60 patients were classified according to C

model but the other 30 to D model. Treating C model patients included: breathing exercises 1 per day for about 30 minutes; 6 times per week of general rehabilitation – 1 per day for about 30 minutes; 3 times a week: walking, recreational activities, inhalation, drainage and percussion. Treating D model patients included: aerobic exercises 2 times per week for about 30 minutes; 6 times a week of specific respiratory workouts, inhalation, drainage and percussion. The physiotherapy program was used six days a week, 3 weeks in accordance with the patients' model. Before and after three weeks of physiotherapy, the collected data was classified and statistically analyzed. For each parameter the mean value and standard deviation have been calculated. The degree of relevance in groups was determined with the T – student test.

The result and its discussion

Walking distance in the six-minutes test and energy consumption is presented in MET.

Determined average walking distance performed by C model patients was 460 (± 85), after physiotherapy it was 523 (± 152). A higher ratio (12%) is observed and it is statistically relevant ($p < 0,001$) (Tab. 1).

It is shown that determined average distance made by D model patients was 435 (± 49), after physiotherapy this was 478 (± 60). Higher ratio (9%) is observed and statistically relevant ($p < 0,001$) (Tab. 2).

The result of research shows that average MET value before rehabilitation in C model patients was 5 (± 2) but after rehabilitation it was 7 (± 3). Higher MET's ratio in the described group is statistically relevant and it is 1 (± 1 , $p < 0,001$) (Tab.1).

It is declared that the average MET value in D model patients before rehabilitation was 5 (± 2), after physiotherapy it was 6 (± 2). Increased MET ratio in presented group is also statistically relevant and it is 5, 5 (± 1 , $p < 0,001$) (Tab. 2).

Tab. 1. Comparison of the results in the group of C model patients before and after rehabilitation.

Before rehabilitation [m]	After rehabilitation [m]	Before rehabilitation [MET]	After rehabilitation [MET]	Arithmetic mean
460 ± 85	523 ± 152	5 ± 2	7 ± 3	
492 ± 45		1 ± 1		Difference
12%		29%		Difference %
p<0,001		p<0,001		T

Tab. 2. Comparison of the results in the group of D model patients before and after rehabilitation.

Before rehabilitation [m]	After rehabilitation [m]	Before rehabilitation [MET]	After rehabilitation [MET]	Arithmetic mean
435 ± 49	478 ± 60	5 ± 1	6 ± 2	
457 ± 30		5,5 ± 1		Difference
9%		17%		Difference %
p<0,001		p<0,001		T

The research conducted shows that comprehensive pulmonary physiotherapy has a significant influence on effort tolerance. On the basis of examinations carried out, doing exercises that are classified according to model C or D has a positive effect on patients. The system presented system helps patients who suffer from asthma to improve the effect of the training. Physiotherapists are able to determine exercises according to the patient's level and evaluate physiotherapy [6].

Conclusion:

1. It is shown that physiotherapy conducted according to model C or D has a significant influence on improvement of effort tolerance.
2. It is stated that a comprehensive model for treatment of asthma increases the walking distance that patients are able to achieve in the six-minutes test.

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Correspondence

mgr Dagmara Matelonek
e-mail: dagmara.matelonek@gmail.com